

Deliverable n. D7.6.

Release of the complete divulgation material

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1. Introduction

This deliverable reports the training materials produced and the capacity-building actions conducted during the second year of the project. These actions aimed to support the adoption of beneficial soil microorganisms and low-input agricultural practices among farmers, technicians, and local stakeholders. It complements the dissemination actions described in D7.5, with a focus on educational content and skill transfer.

2. Objectives

- Develop practical and localized training materials for end-users.
- Build capacity in sustainable agricultural practices across the partner countries.
- Reinforce stakeholder engagement and knowledge transfer.
- Contribute directly to **Milestone 7.3** and **Milestone 7.5**, ensuring the implementation of local training and outreach.

3. Description of Training Materials

3.1 Brochure – Tunisia (April 2024)

Title: *Gestion durable des cultures de figuier de Barbarie à l'aide de biointrants microbiens*

- Focus: Application of biofertilizers and beneficial fungi in *Opuntia* plantations.
- Context: Produced for the technical training held in Tunisia in collaboration with local cooperatives.

Link to Milestone 7.5: Supports training activities in southern Tunisia and diffusion of the new microbial technology.

3.2 Brochure – Morocco (September 2023)

Title: *Microorganismes du sol et pratiques agricoles durables : Application au figuier de Barbarie*

- Produced following the workshop in Essaouira with the cooperative.
- Contents: Definitions, types of beneficial microbes, field application techniques, safety, and economic benefits.

Link to Milestone 7.3: Field-based outreach and dissemination in North Morocco aligned with farmer needs.

3.3 Brochure – Algeria (January–February 2024)

Title: *Utilisation des micro-organismes bénéfiques pour améliorer la productivité agricole*

- Sections: Introduction to microbial products, preparation techniques, compost integration, monitoring.
- Target audience: Young farmers, technicians, extension agents.

Link to Milestone 7.3 & 7.5: Implements local training campaigns and contributes to milestone validation in Algeria.

4. Visual Documentation

- Annexes include photos of field training.
- Summary of participants: 120+ farmers across the 3 countries.

6. Feedback and Impact

- Participants appreciated the clarity and relevance of the materials.